

DIGITALIZATION, AUTOMATION AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN THE ECONOMY OF THE XXI CENTURY

Khakimjanova S.Kh.

Assistant teacher, Tashkent State Technical University named after Islam Karimov

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14195853>

Abstract. *In the context of rapid changes caused by globalization and technological breakthroughs, the role of innovative technologies in the economy is becoming more and more significant. Innovations not only change the approaches to production and management, but also contribute to the creation of new markets, transformation of business models and increasing the competitiveness of countries and companies, transformation of labor, as well as discuss the challenges and risks associated with their implementation. Understanding these dynamics is key to the formation of effective economic policies and successful development in a rapidly changing world.*

Keywords: *economic policies, innovative technologies, ERP, CRM, SAP, IoT (Internet of Things).*

Introduction: In the context of rapid changes caused by globalization and technological breakthroughs, the role of innovative technologies in the economy is becoming increasingly important. Innovation not only changes the way we produce and manage, but also contributes to the creation of new markets, the transformation of business models and the competitiveness of countries and companies. In this article, we will look at how innovative technologies affect economic growth, job creation and transformation of labor, as well as discuss the challenges and risks associated with their implementation. Understanding these dynamics is key to the formation of effective economic policies and successful development in a rapidly changing world.

There are different types of innovative technologies such as information technology, biotechnology, environmental technology, nanotechnology, medical technology, agro-industrial technology and others. Innovative technologies significantly contribute to increasing productivity in various sectors of the economy. They allow to optimize processes, reduce costs, improve product quality and speed up time to market.

Implementing automation on production lines and in offices helps reduce task lead times and errors. For example, the use of robots in the production of cars can significantly increase the volume of products while reducing labor costs. Modern management systems (ERP, CRM) allow companies to effectively plan and control resources, which leads to lower costs and increased overall efficiency. For example, SAP offers solutions that help businesses integrate various processes and improve interaction between departments. For example, Amazon uses machine learning algorithms to predict demand, allowing them to manage inventory efficiently and reduce shipping times. Companies that implement new technologies in their products can offer customers better and more convenient solutions. For example, Apple is constantly updating its devices with new technologies, which not only increases demand but also allows them to remain market leaders.

We know that a lot of companies in different countries have greatly expanded their potential when using innovations, for example, in the United States, Silicon Valley is a symbol of innovation, where many startups and large companies (for example, Google, Facebook) are

developing new technologies that contribute to economic growth and increase productivity. These companies are actively using IT and big data to create new products and services. South Korea also actively invests in high technology and innovative solutions, which has made the country one of the leaders in the field of electronics and information technology. Companies such as Samsung and LG use advanced technologies to develop innovative products, which contributes to their global competitiveness. Germany is implementing the concept of "Industry 4.0", which is based on the use of IoT (Internet of Things) and automation in production. Companies such as Siemens and Bosch are actively developing smart factories, which can significantly increase productivity and reduce production costs. China is becoming a global leader in technologies such as artificial intelligence and 5G. Huawei, for example, is actively developing its networks and technologies, which contributes to the rapid development of other industries and increases the overall productivity of the economy.

Thus, the adoption of innovative technologies is an important factor that contributes to increased productivity and economic growth, both at the level of individual companies and entire countries. These examples show that investing in innovation can lead to significant competitive advantages and sustainable development.

Innovative technologies are radically changing the structure of employment and the requirements for workers, creating new professions and transforming existing ones. The introduction of automated systems and robots in the manufacturing and service sectors leads to a decrease in the need for labor to perform routine tasks. For example, in many factories, traditional operations are being replaced by robotic systems, which can lead to job cuts in certain occupations. At the same time, technology is creating new professions that require specific skills. Data scientists, analysts, software developers, and cybersecurity experts are just a few of the new roles that are becoming in demand in the digital economy. Today's employers are looking for employees with advanced digital skills, adaptability, and creative thinking. For example, skills in big data, artificial intelligence, and cloud technologies are becoming essential for success in most industries.

In order to maintain economic growth and energy security, Uzbekistan will transition to a green economy in stages by 2030. According to this concept for the development of the energy sector, the total demand of the Republic of Uzbekistan for electricity by 2030 will increase to 120.8 billion kWh or 1.86 times compared to 2019, an increase of an average of 5.8% per year.

The introduction of green technologies plays an important role in the energy sector in terms of fuel economy, and also plays a major role in reducing emissions into the atmosphere. Uzbekistan has set targets for renewable energy generation and capacity. The country plans to produce 25% of its electricity from its own renewable sources by 2030 and intends to increase its energy capacity by adding 7 GW of solar energy and 5 GW of wind energy.

Targets for the construction of solar power plants until 2030

Table 1

Solar stations	17
Total capacity of projects	7000 MW
Total cost of projects	\$4.8 billion
Annual Output	15.3 billion kW.
Annual Natural Gas Savings	4.5 billion cubic meters.

Targets for the construction of wind farms until 2030

Table 2

Number of projects	11
Total capacity of projects	5000 MW
Total cost of projects	\$6.0 billion
Annual Output	17.5 billion kW.
Annual Natural Gas Savings	5.2 billion cubic meters.
Reduction of annual harmful emissions	6.7 million tons.

The key priorities for Uzbekistan in the field of green energy are: improving infrastructure, supporting private investment, as well as integrating renewable sources into the national energy system. Numerous large projects for the construction of solar and wind power plants, as well as legislative initiatives aimed at creating a more favorable environment for investors, indicate the seriousness of the country's intentions in implementing its environmental and energy policies. However, additional efforts are needed to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals and increase the share of renewable energy in the national energy mix. Challenges related to infrastructure modernization, high capital costs, and the need for technical integration of variable energy remain challenges that require an integrated approach. In general, the development of green energy in Uzbekistan opens up new opportunities for economic growth, improving the environmental situation and increasing the country's energy security. This area has prospects for creating new jobs, attracting foreign investment and integrating the country into global energy and environmental trends.

In conclusion, supporting innovation is a fundamental element for achieving sustainable economic development. Taking the necessary measures to manage risks and ensure equal access to new technologies will create a more equitable and prosperous society. Innovative technologies will undoubtedly become the basis of the future economy, forming new horizons for growth and development.

REFERENCES

1. Data of the Ministry of Energy of Uzbekistan on the introduction of renewable energy in the country.
2. "European Union – Central Asia: Cooperation on Water, Environment and Climate Change" (WECOOP).
3. <https://wecoop.eu/ru/glossary/green-deal/>
4. Journal. UN Chronicle. Water is on the agenda.
5. Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. United Nations, 2015.
6. Workshop "Enhancing Cross-Border Energy Cooperation through the Introduction of Wind and Solar Energy into the Energy Systems of the CIS Member States to Achieve SDG 7".
7. Problems in the integration of renewable energy sources into the energy system of Uzbekistan and recommendations for their solution. Ph.D. Shamsiev Kh.A., Director of CDC "Energy", Almaty, December 2021
8. Annual report of the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022.
9. Review of policies affecting air pollution from the electricity sector in Central Asia

10. Russian translation of An Overview of Policies Influencing Air Pollution from the Electricity Sector in Central Asia (<https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy23osti/81861.pdf>)
11. Eric Ness, Garvin Xit, and Vicram Ravi.
12. National Renewable Energy Laboratory
13. <https://web.stanford.edu/group/efmh/jacobson/Articles/I/WWS-145-Countries.html>